

Editorial Word

Thanks to the gentle collaboration of the authors that took part in issue 0 of *Contextos kantianos. International Journal of Philosophy*, it is possible to launch now the issue 1 of a journal, whose sections and contents will be shaped by the rightful main characters of the journal: its authors and readers. I wish to specially thank all the colleagues that allowed introducing this new journal with the issue 0. Among them, CTK editorial ought to highlight the contribution of the excellent and very active *Grupo de Estudios Kantianos* (GEK) of the University of Buenos Aires (Argentina), founded by Mario Caimi and currently coordinated by Hernán Pringe.

I ought to specially thank the always friendly encouragement of the prestigious Latin American Kant scholar, María Julia Bertomeu (Scientific Research National Council/University of La Plata, Argentina), one of the associated editors, who supported me from the initial launching of the journal. This special thanks must be sincerely extended to the terrific colleagues, Catalina González (University of Los Andes, Colombia), Eduardo Molina (University Alberto Hurtado, Chile) y Efraín Lazos (UNAM Institute for Philosophical Research, México), who generously accepted to be also Associated Editors of the journal. I would like to mention also here the name of another prominent Kant scholar, Faviola Rivera (IIF-UNAM), who signed with María Julia Bertomeu and me the first *call for papers* for selecting the members of CTK Editorial Board (29) and Advisor Board (32). *Last but not least*, I would like to specially highlight the impressive enthusiasm of Nuria Sánchez Madrid (University Complutense of Madrid, Spain), CTK Executive Secretary. She coordinates the mailing and the layout tasks of the journal, which she undertook during a sabbatical stay at the IFS-CSIC. Her contribution has been essential for preparing the first two issues of *CTK*.

After setting up the wide Editorial Team, some members of the Editorial Board began taking over concrete tasks, as the coordination of the journal's book reviews section. Here *Con-Textos Kantianos* counts on the outstanding cooperation of a remarkable international group of Kant scholars, composed by Ileana Beade (National University of Rosario, Argentina), Antonino Falduto (University of Halle, Germany), Marceline Morais (Cégep Saint Laurent, Montréal, Canada), Pablo Muchnik (Emerson College, United States), Cinara Nahra (UFRN, Brasil) and Margit Ruffing (University of Mainz, Germany). I thank all of them for their commitment with the journal. Finally, I thank to Ana-Carolina

Gutiérrez-Xivillé (Philipps-University Marburg, Germany/University of Barcelona, Spain), the youngest member of the editorial team, for her excellent work for preparing the CTK newsletter, which will be out with each miscellaneous issue of the journal.

As it is obvious, this publishing project gets coming progressively true thanks to a sort of “academic crowd patronage”, which shaped the above mentioned fruitful distribution of tasks. At the core of our “crowd founding”, I shall mention Armando Menéndez, who designed our logo header, Nuria Roca, who developed the layout matrix, and Javier Davó, who continues being our webmaster.

The contributions of this issue bear witness of the international commitment of the journal, which takes care of the linguistic richness of the current Kant studies, without neglecting its Latin American scope. In fact, the sections of the current issue (Interviews, Articles, Notes and Discussions, Translations of Kant’s texts, Documents, Book Reviews and Newsletter) contain texts in German, Spanish, French, English, Italian and Portuguese. In this issue appears a new section, called “Documents”, which aims at publishing short texts authored by outstanding Kant scholars, not previously published or not more available in Spanish. Next issues could contain also a new section, called “Dossier”, which will gather different papers focused on a common subject and discussed at Kant-related Congresses or Workshops. Naturally, the appearance in our next tables of contents of all these sections will depend on the contribution of authors. Next issue will be monographic, as all pair issues, while odd issues will be miscellaneous.

The *call for papers* of the first monographic it is available from April 2015 at *Con-textos kantianos* website and it was also kindly spread with the help of different international Kant Societies, as the *NAKS*, the *Società Italiana di Studi Kantiani* or the *SEKLE*. Also the *Red Española de Filosofía* helped us to make the CFP circulate. Finally, I have to thank particularly all the colleagues who collaborated with us from 2014 for launching the peer review process of the papers submitted to the journal. They are already part of our starting valuable evaluators’ bank.

Berlin, June of 2015
Roberto R. Aramayo
CTK Chief Editor

